

PEDAGOGICAL ASPECTS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF DIDACTIC COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS IN THE PROCESS OF PROFESSIONAL RETRAINING

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Abstract. *Today, the educational process in a modern school is aimed at ensuring that students, including primary schoolchildren, acquire enough knowledge to independently creatively solve theoretical or practical problems, and to achieve this goal, teachers teach subjects, it is important that they organize the educational process with the help of objects and tools, are ready to explore their problems and have the opportunity to organize educational activities.*

Keywords: *professional retraining, students, advanced training, personal development, teacher, professional activity.*

In order to improve the system of retraining of teaching staff, it is important to implement the following:

- consider and identify the strengths and weaknesses of existing methods of retraining primary school teachers;
- identification and implementation of new methods and models of training;
- decision-making and development of recommendations for reforming the work of primary school teachers;
- understanding the characteristics and requirements of the field of primary school teacher training;
- creation of a model for improving the teacher retraining system.

According to the analysis, the most necessary factor for the development of quality education is cooperation in the scientific and technical field, which is important for the retraining of teachers. This is necessary to acquire new information and skills for retraining.

Also, improving the quality of teacher retraining requires effective solutions to the following issues:

1. To what extent does the current education system affect the professional and professional potential of teachers?
2. What is the most important reason why teachers fail in in-service learning?
3. To what extent are new methods and models used in the existing teacher training system?
4. What methods and strategies are used to improve the quality of teacher preparation?
5. How to determine the desired characteristics of a specialty profession, depending on the model?

In accordance with the educational requirements for teachers in the courses, it is necessary to take into account the fundamental issues of teaching students using traditional teaching methods [9], since the courses emphasize the basic skills of increasing the creative abilities of students. It is important to ensure the quality of teaching and efficiency [10].

According to T.T. Shaimardonov “in the development of professional competence and skills of a teacher, the formation of sufficient theoretical and practical knowledge in the field of the fundamentals of individual subjects, the ability to effectively use advanced pedagogical and information and communication technologies in the educational process, and continuous independent professional development, the determination of motivation is also one of the important factors”, he believes [5].

According to Muslimov [4], “Competence is expressed in the student’s acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities necessary to carry out personal and socially significant professional activities, and the ability to apply them in professional activities. In this place, the essence of the concept of “competence” is fully revealed; it manifests itself in the following two forms: competence as a set of personal qualities of students and the basic requirements of the professional sphere [4].

In his research S.Y. Makhmudov work, developed a structure of professional development in accordance with the levels of preparation for teaching activity (level of action, required level, level of local change in the pedagogical system and level of the author’s system), which includes four components: knowledge, experience of practical and intellectual activity and the experience of an emotional and value-based attitude to reality,” he states [3].

All these descriptions are aimed at improving the process of developing the didactic competence of students in the process of professional retraining: ensuring the quality and effectiveness of education through the use of innovative technologies in the educational process, educational activities to develop the didactic competence of students and the organization. trainings to improve knowledge; conducting trainings to ensure the organization of the educational process in accordance with foreign experience; improvement of teaching practice and technologies based on the development of didactic competence, achieving joint solutions to students’ professional problems. It is noted that the ability of students to acquire and apply knowledge in teaching activities, to effectively organize the educational process, to have large resources of knowledge and skills for continuous self-professional development should serve to develop their didactic competence. made.

Teacher retraining is considered as follows: from an educational point of view, it provides systematic and continuous improvement that helps personnel in the areas of their formation, knowledge, skills and behavior patterns. In other words, education, knowledge and experience serve to improve professional standing.

Researchers say that creating a flexible learning environment consists of changing information and skills. So, taking into account the above definitions, we can conclude that the main goal is the development of education, knowledge and skills. It is a process of continuous education and empowerment in relation to achieving the final result, improving abilities, potential, personal qualities, as well as personal development.

Many opinions have been expressed on the issue of professional retraining: on its basis, issues of student training, “purposeful mutual cooperation of teachers and students,” “acquisition of scientific knowledge and skills,” and the pedagogical process are resolved. active educational activities aimed at developing creative abilities, ideological, spiritual, ethical, and aesthetic views are organized and encouraged. [11, 12, 13]). Professional retraining is a process of educational activities and is a type of cognition, cognitive activity or knowledge, conscious and firmly acquired knowledge, skills and abilities, the application of developed skills in life, the development of

independent creative thinking, observation, etc. a set of consistent and interconnected actions of the teacher and students in directed interaction [11, 12, 13].

Each of the above definitions certainly has the right to exist; the reason is a separate experience, manifested in the form of stages that reveal the essence of education. However, individually, these definitions of teaching and similar definitions cannot reveal its essence. Evidence of this may include experience teaching and teaching specific knowledge, qualifications and skills.

However, knowledge, skills and abilities arise in the human brain, in a person, only as a result of personal activity. They cannot simply be accepted; they arise as a result of the student's mental activity and, above all, in his thinking.

The process of professional retraining is a purposeful collaboration between a teacher and a student, during which the educational problems of students are solved [7].

However, this interaction is very clear, implementation mechanisms are indicated, and accordingly, the essence of education should be imagined as an integral pedagogical phenomenon. In this process, the emphasis is placed not only on the teacher and the listener as subjects of activity, but also on their personal characteristics, their consistently developing activities in purposeful, interdependent relationships.

In this process, learning is expressed as educational activity, and the educational process is expressed as an exchange of states of the system of activities created by the subjects themselves. However, by focusing on the content of the educational process itself, the authors missed an important point from this definition, because the system of teaching and learning activities is not only created by the people themselves, but also exists separately from them. , this is done by them and through them. It exists to realize certain goals of society [8].

Experts put forward different definitions. Here are some of them:

Education, upbringing is a purposeful process of education and training that meets the interests of the individual, society and the state, organized by the state and the achievement by a citizen (student) of a given level of education. The level of general and secondary education is based on the requirements of the state of production, science, technology and culture, as well as social relations. In the broadest sense of the word, education is "...the process or product of shaping the mind, character or physical abilities of a person." In the technical sense of the word, education is the process by which a society, through schools, colleges, universities and other institutions, transmits its culture - the knowledge, values and skills accumulated over time as heritage - from one generation to another. next [3].

In addition to transmitting the content of sociocultural heritage, the social development of education has allowed a person to disconnect from the nature of cognition and interaction for long periods of life. Currently, through education, a person uses the life experience of his ancestors and introduces it to social development [1].

Future research into our problem needs to think a little more deeply about teaching and learning. The reason is that this is very important from the point of view of the problem of enriching and optimizing the content of the requirements for the quality of professional retraining courses for granting the right to teach in the primary classes in question. On the other hand, we logically connect the concept of "retraining" with the concepts of "education" and "training". From this point of view, education is inherently based on the content and methods of teaching, teaching

aids, implementation and evaluation of programs. He will have the opportunity to learn to create a creative environment to optimize this process.

The duality of the educational process plays an important leading role as its characteristic. In this process, new information is assimilated, skills and abilities are developed, and the education and creative talent of students develops.

In fact, the educational process involves mutual cooperation between the teacher and students, but only mutual cooperation is not enough to obtain solid and deep knowledge. It is necessary to think about how to organize the educational and cognitive activity of students, constantly intensify and stimulate it. It often happens that while explaining a lesson, the teacher-teacher cannot arouse interest in the material being taught and is forced to reassure the students, so the students may not have the desire to learn new knowledge. In this case, training does not give effective results [6].

It is necessary to pay special attention to such features of upbringing. If in the educational process direct communication is ensured during the interaction between the teacher and students, then how is the independent educational process, which is considered an important part of education, implemented. Therefore, the educational process should be built using such methods that in the learning process students acquire new knowledge, acquire new skills, develop their creative abilities, stimulate their educational and cognitive activities by forming their spiritual and moral aesthetic views. and worldview.

The given description allows us to formulate tasks for the development of didactic competence of students in the process of professional retraining. (Look Figure 1)

Figure 1. Tasks for developing didactic competence of students in the process of professional retraining

Thus, the objectives of the educational process are the result of deeply conscious goals put forward by the teacher before training or education, as well as the conditions and methods that help realize these goals in practice.

The retraining process as a system consists of the following components: the goals of retraining, the activities of the teacher (training leader) and students (listeners) and the final result. These components also have their own elements. The variable conditions of this process include management tools: the content of the material being studied and the methods used in the educational process, technical aids, textbooks (materials), technical teaching aids, organizational forms of training, the process reflects the teacher's activities for improvement.

The goals of retraining and their final result take into account the interdependence and interdependence of educational means - permanent and episodic. They create an environment of unity and integrity designed to prepare teachers for active work in a modern school environment, taking into account the goals of educational integration and general retraining.

The element that unites all the above components is joint activity in teaching and learning activities, a necessary component of which is communication.

For this reason, the process of teacher retraining is integrated as a system and has a holistic connection of integrated concepts. It consists of many interrelated elements: educational information, goals, communication between teachers and students using the results of managing all types of teacher retraining activities, consists of tools, forms and methods.

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